
Preprint Research Article

Repurposing Pheophorbide a as an Antiviral Molecule for Targeting a Stable Region in the Human papillomavirus type 16 GenomeRagıp Soner Silme^{1*} ¹ Istanbul University, Center for Research and Practice in Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, Fatih-Istanbul, Türkiye, rsoner@istanbul.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0001-6547-3747

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The emergence of Human papillomavirus (HPV) among the human population in different regions of the world has heightened the interest for new treatment methods. Molecular docking is a reliable and predictive method for screening of new potential antiviral molecules against pathogens. The retrieved 42 high-quality whole-genome sequences of HPV were analysed in view of a stable region existence in the genome. The protein encoded by this stable region was targeted for protein-ligand interaction. Consequently, a target constant region which is responsible for encoding the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain with various regulatory functions for the virus, was detected. A ligand “Pheophorbide a (C₃₅H₃₆N₄O₅)” interacts with this protein, which could be used against HPV. As known, Pheophorbide a has also been commercially used for cancer treatments. The predictive results need confirmation with further clinical and *in vitro* studies. The findings will provide new insights into HPV-human cell interactions, induced immunity, and new methods for HPV treatment.

1. Introduction

Human papillomaviruses (HPVs) are small, non-enveloped DNA viruses that are ubiquitously present in nature and constitute a diverse viral family, encompassing both benign and highly carcinogenic variants [1]. HPVs primarily replicate within the surface layers of squamous epithelia, particularly at the junctions between squamous epithelial cells and the columnar epithelium of the cervix. This replication can disrupt normal squamous cell proliferation, resulting in abnormal epithelial growth [2]. As non-lytic infections, HPVs typically do not provoke a robust immune response or inflammation because they do not activate Toll-like receptors or natural killer cells [3].

To date, > 170 HPV types have been identified, with > 40 of these linked to infections in the female reproductive tract and cervical lesions [4]. HPV types are generally classified into high-risk and low-risk categories based on their pathogenic potential. Low-risk types, such as HPV6, HPV11, and HPV30, are associated with benign lesions, including lower-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions and genital warts. In contrast, high-risk types, such as HPV16, HPV18, and HPV58, are primarily responsible for the development of higher-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions and cervical cancer [5].

In Europe, cervical cancer is the second leading cause of death among young women, with nearly 24,400 deaths reported annually [6]. HPV can be present in various anatomical sites, including the

genital and urinary tracts, as well as the throat and mouth [7]. Several cofactors have been identified in the development of cervical cancer, including prolonged use of oral contraceptives, sexually transmitted infections, and smoking; however, their influence is considered minor compared with the role of persistent HPV infection [8]. Approximately 43% of vulvar, 70% of vaginal, and 100% of cervical tumors are associated with HPV [9]. Although HPV is most commonly transmitted through sexual intercourse, non-sexual transmission routes, such as perinatal vertical transmission and physical contact, have also been reported [10].

Some international pharmaceutical companies have developed various HPV vaccines based on virus-like particles derived from the *L1* major capsid protein [11]. Although these vaccines have become part of government vaccination programmes in over 100 countries [12-15], there are some concerns about their side effects, and their long-term effects are unknown [16-23]. Therefore, new alternative HPV treatment methods are also necessary.

In this study, the unvarying regions of Human papillomavirus type 16 were investigated in 42 various genome sequences available in the NCBI database. This study aims to identify stable regions in the viral genome to perform prediction of protein structure and docking analysis to determine an effective molecule interacting with a protein of HPV for preventing its virulence.

2. General Methods

2.1. Homology genome blast and genome information

A total of 42 complete HPV type 16 genome sequences were retrieved from the NCBI database as of August 13, 2024. The dataset included only complete genomes with high coverage. The genomes are listed in Table 1 (Supplementary data S1).

2.2. Phylogenetic analysis

HPV sequences were aligned by using Geneious Prime software version 2024.0.7 (Biomatters Ltd., Auckland, New Zealand). In order to build phylogenetic tree for the recent genomes, the Tamura-Nei-parameters genetic distance model and the Neighbor-Joining were selected with sorted topologies.

2.3. Nucleotide and amino acid sequence alignment and analysis

The sequences were analysed, and common regions of all genomes were detected from pairwise alignment results using Progressive-MAUVE from the Geneious software (Geneious Prime® 2024.0.7) (Supplementary data S2).

Each unvarying genomic region was excised from whole sequences and subjected to the protein similarity programme of the NCBI database using BlastX. The obtained FASTA sequence was converted to protein sequence using the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate/>) [26] and then loaded to the I-TASSER (Iterative Threading ASSEMBly Refinement) server of Michigan University, US (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) for protein prediction [27].

2.4. Homology modelling and protein prediction

The corresponding homology models predicted by the ITASSER server system for the target protein were downloaded from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (www.rcsb.org) (Table 2). Alignment of the protein sequences and subsequent homology modelling were performed using the ExPASy proteomics server for further structural details [28].

Table 1. The 42 selected whole-genome sequences of Human papillomavirus type 16 were used for MAUVE analysis. “-“ represents unknown. RefSeq; Reference Sequence. The sequences are listed alphabetically by country of origin

NCBI Accession Number	Country of Origin	Isolation Source	Bp Length	Collection/Submission Date
K02718.1	-	human invasive cervical carcinoma	7904	1985/1993
KU053823.1	-	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2015
HM057182.1	Amazonian-Brazil	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7915	2007/2010
HQ644234.1	Asia	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2010
KP874717.1	Brazil	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7847	2015
KU298880.1	Brazil	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2015
KC935953.1	China	cervical cancer	7906	2013
KF954093.1	China	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2013
MT783409.1	China	vaginal secretions	7908	2016/2020
MK484705.1	China	perianal tumor tissue	7912	2018/2019
EU918764.1	China: Gansu province	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7904	2007/2008
MH892050.1	China: Northeast region	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2017/2018
MW320358.1	China: Northeast region	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7909	2017/2020
FJ006723.1	China: Xinjiang province	Uygur cervical cancer patient	7963	2006/2008
JN565302.1	Croatia	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7973	2001/2011
AF534061.1	East Asia	Cervicovaginal Cells	7905	2002
EU118173.1	Germany	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2007
KY883659.1	India	cervical specimen	7906	2017
KU684311.1	India	cervical carcinoma	7916	2011/2016
LC511105.1	Japan	invasive cervical cancer	7688	2019
LC456180.1	Japan	Cervix	7904	2019
LC193821.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2016
LC368952.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2018
LC718895.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2021/2022
LC786753.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2021/2023
AB889488.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2013
LC647437.1	Japan	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2021
LR861897.1	Luxembourg	cervical swap	7906	2015/2020
MN961210.1	Mexico	cervical brushing for liquid-based cytology	7908	2020
KX947269.1	Nepal	cervical samples	7906	2014/2016
KY549156.1	Netherlands	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7905	2017
OQ911727.1	Pakistan	oropharynx from patient with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma	7171	2017/2023
OP971046.1	South Africa	Vaginal secretion	7886	2017
KY994539.1	Sweden	tonsillar carcinoma	7904	2014/2017
KF880690.1	Sweden	tonsillar carcinoma	7906	2011/2013
FJ610146.1	Thailand	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2008/2009
JQ004092.1	Thailand	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7911	2010/2011
OP711986.1	Togo	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7904	2017/2022
OP751552.1	United Kingdom	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7908	2016/2022
AF125673.1	USA	human foreskin keratinocyte cell line	7904	1995/1999
AY686579.1	USA	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2004
NC_001526.4 (RefSeq)	USA	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7906	2000

2.5. Ligand retrieval

The structure of Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$) was retrieved from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). This structure was used for docking calculations. The selected 3D structure of the ligand was then

retrieved from the PubChem Compound database in SDF format. The ligand parameters were analysed using the PRODRG online server (<http://prodr2.dyndns.org/cgi-bin/prodr2.cgi>) [29]. The shape complementarity principle was applied with clustering RMSD 4.0 for docking calculations.

2.6 Molecular docking studies

Homology modelling and protein prediction analysis have directed us to test the gene responsible for the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain, with the ligand. The flexible docking study was conducted using AutoDock v 4.0 [30]. The interaction analysis of protein-ligand complexes and their amino acid positions with bond distances were calculated and visualised using PyMol. Molecular docking simulation results were also confirmed using the protein dock server SWISSDOCK (<http://www.swissdock.ch/docking>) within protein receptors and ligand interactions [31]. Pymol software was used to gain insight into their all-binding preferences within the active site of the receptor.

Table 2. Homology modelling of the HPV E7 CR3 protein using ITASSER (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) considering the specific sequence. *The highest PDB hit was 2ew1A

Rank	PDB Hit	Identity 1	Identity 2	Coverage	Norm. Z-score
1*	2ew1A	0.37	0.24	0.55	1.25
2	7evaC	0.07	0.13	0.89	0.76
3	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.57	5.09
4	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.57	3.50
5	2ew1A	0.36	0.24	0.56	2.79
6	2ew1	0.38	0.24	0.53	5.26
7	2ew1A	0.38	0.24	0.57	1.13
8	2ew1A	0.38	0.24	0.57	2.29
9	8fw5G	0.11	0.24	0.96	0.52
10	2f8bA	0.38	0.24	0.57	2.35

3. Results

3.1. Phylogenetic tree

The maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree shows 2 main clades; one branch with 5 sequences (Figure 1-a) and another branch with 37 sequences (Figure 1-b) with several clusters. Only within b group there is geographically similarity within 15 sequences (Figure 1-b1). The rest of viral genome sequences exhibited geographical difference and distributed in phylogenetic tree, respectively. Figure 1 presents the genetic diversity of HPV 16 sequences from different regions of the world.

3.2. Nucleotide and amino acid sequence alignment and analysis

Our results showed high mutational changes in whole genomes, except for the region between

100 and 850 bp, which is a constantly unvarying part of whole sequences (Figure 2).

3.3. Homology modelling and protein prediction

The excised uniform regions of sequences subjected to alignment for protein similarity indicated that the 750-bp region included the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 protein with constantly unvarying sequences (Figure 2). These stable sequences were selected as a template for further protein structural predictions (Figure 2). The results of the submitted sequence converted to amino acid sequence using the Expasy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate>) were structurally very close to the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain (www.rcsb.org/structure/2b9d) [32] as a target protein according to I-TASSER analysis, and its ligand was determined as Chlorophyll a. Pheophorbide a (C₃₅H₃₆N₄O₅), a small molecule, and Chlorophyll a derivative, which is commercially produced and widely used for anticancer studies, was selected as a ligand for molecular docking analysis (Supplementary data S3-S4).

Figure 1. The phylogenetic tree of HPV represents 2 main branches, labeled as (a) and (b). Geographic comparison results show two groups among (b): (b1) genomes sequences from Asian countries and (b2) various sequences from different countries. Group (a) also includes geographically various countries

Figure 2. Progressive MAUVE analysis presented a stable region shown in light green-yellow (marked with red arrow) among all HPV genomes

MHGDPTLHEYMLDLQPETTDLYCYEQLNDSSE
 EEDEIDGPAGQAEPDRAHYNIVTFCCKCDSTLRL
 CVQSTHVDIRLTLEDLLMGTLGIVCPICSQKP

Figure 3. The results of submitted sequence were converted to amino acid sequence using the Expasy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate>) for structural analysis using the I-TASSER server

Figure 4. Visualisation depicts docking analysis of Pheophorbide a binding with crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain (PDB: 2b9d.1) (A) hydrophobicity surface 3D representation (B) interaction of Pheophorbide a with 2b9d.1 (C) visualisation of hydrogen bond (D) visualisation of hydrophobic interaction (E) 2D representation describes the bindings of Pheophorbide a with the active site of 2b9d.1

3.4. Molecular docking studies

For docking analysis of Pheophorbide a with the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain (PDB: 2b9d.1), the ligand structure of Pheophorbide a retrieved from the PubChem database, was analysed (Fig. 2-4). Docking of 2b9d.1 with

the target molecule Pheophorbide a was studied with respect to the following parameters: (a) interacting amino acids (b) ligand and protein atoms involved in hydrogen bonding (Supplementary data S3-S4). The SWISSDOCK server results confirmed the outputs obtained from AutoDock software calculations (Fig. 2-4).

4. Discussion

Papillomaviruses constitute a diverse group of DNA viruses characterised by closed, circular, double-stranded DNA genomes approximately 8 kilobases (kb) in size, organised into three general regions. The upstream regulatory region (URR) contains sequences essential for transcriptional and replicative control. The early region encodes genes such as *E6*, *E7*, *E1*, *E2*, *E4*, and *E5*, which primarily contribute to enzymatic functions. The structural region encodes the *L1* capsid protein and *L2*, which plays a role in viral DNA packaging. HPVs are classified based on the sequence similarity of their genomes, with novel HPV types defined as those whose *L1* open reading frame exhibits less than 90% similarity to previously identified types. To date, more than 90 HPV genotypes have been fully characterised [4, 33]. Intratypic variants and subtypes are defined as HPVs that vary by less than 10% in their *L1* DNA sequences [33, 34].

HPVs play a causal role in the development of cervical cancer (CC) and its precursor lesions [35–38]. Among the high-risk HPV types linked to cervical cancer, HPV16 is the most prevalent, being detected in approximately 50% of CC cases [38, 39]. Multiple variants of HPV16 have been identified across diverse geographic regions and ethnic groups [40–43]. Despite their genetic similarity, five distinct phylogenetic branches of HPV16 variants have been classified based on geographic origin: European, Asian, Asian-American, African-1, and African-2 [44, 45]. Subsequent sequence analyses of additional genomic regions, such as *E6*, *L2*, and *L1* have further refined and supported this phylogenetic framework [46]. In this study, phylogenetic analysis revealed two primary branches, denoted as (a) and (b). Within branch (b), two subgroups were identified, of which only subgroup (b1) demonstrated geographic alignment with Asian countries (Figure 1).

Although HPV16 variants have been extensively studied in the context of phylogenetics, with detailed descriptions of molecular variations in the *E2*, *L2*, *L1*, URR, and especially the *E6* region [47], genetic variation stability of genes within the same lineage or isolate has received limited attention. HPV16 variants exhibit notable

differences in biological properties *in vitro*, which may contribute to variations in pathogenicity, carcinogenic potential, and possibly immunogenicity [47]. Additionally, specific HPV16 variants are linked to varying risks of cervical cancer development [48–51]. Although diversifying selection in the *E6* and *E7* oncogenes has been recently documented [52], the evolutionary dynamics of the entire genome, the coevolutionary interactions among different HPV16 genes, and their biological implications remain unclear.

Among the evolutionary basis of the entire genome, some genes emerge as the sole segment displaying a uniform sequence, distinct from the remaining portion of the genome. The proteins encoded by these regions could be considered as a target point for the purpose of targeted drug design, as described in “*Baysal’s hypothesis*” [53], and the results from previous studies also confirmed this hypothesis [54–57].

The conserved region of HPV 16 which was determined to be responsible for coding the crystal structure of HPV E7 CR3 domain through Progressive-MAUVE analysis in this study. HR-HPVs encode three oncogenes, *E5*, *E6*, and *E7* [58, 59], and among these, *E7* appears to be the main driver of cervical carcinogenesis [60].

The E7 oncoprotein is primarily recognised for its interaction with and degradation of the pRb tumor suppressor protein [61]. It also associates with other cellular proteins involved in cell cycle regulation, transcriptional repression, and tumor suppression [61–63]. In murine models, the combination of HPV16 E7 and exogenous estrogen has been shown to be sufficient to induce high-grade cervical dysplasia and cervical cancer [60, 64, 65], while causing significant alterations in the expression of numerous cellular genes [66]. Moreover, sustained expression of fully functional viral oncoproteins E6 and E7 is essential for maintaining extrachromosomal forms of HPV DNA [67]. These oncoproteins contribute to creating a cellular environment favourable for HPV persistence by circumventing cellular checkpoints that would otherwise hinder the long-term retention of extrachromosomal DNA [67–69]. Viral oncogenes have the capacity to disrupt cell-cycle

control checkpoints by interfering with the regulatory mechanisms of cyclins, cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), and CDK inhibitors [70–72].

This study exhibited the molecule that interacts with E7 protein is Chlorophyll a and Pheophorbide a. These molecules could suppress the E7 oncoprotein, resulting in dysfunction of HPVs' replication machinery. Previous studies have indicated the presence of different HPV subtypes in the same tissue in clinical samples, suggesting that the frequency of co-infections may be quite high [73]. Since the E7 oncoprotein also plays a central role in many other HPV types, this possible antiviral property of Pheophorbide a should be tested on other high-risk and low-risk Papillomaviruses.

Chlorophylls are prominent bioactive compounds known for their significant health benefits, including anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties [74, 75]. Among their various positive effects, chlorophylls exhibit potent antioxidant activity, mitigating oxidative DNA damage and lipid peroxidation by reducing reactive oxygen species (ROS) and chelating metal ions [75–78]. Notably, Chlorophyll-a and its metabolites accumulate in specific tissues, such as the liver and gut, suggesting that these organs could be particularly influenced by their positive biological activity [79, 80].

The chemical nature of porphyrin allows Chlorophylls to function as hydrogen donors, stopping the oxidative chain reaction [81]. Pheophorbide a is a derivative of Chlorophyll a [82]. Interestingly, the porphyrin structure of these two molecules and human blood cell hemoglobin are similar (Figure 5).

Previous studies have indicated that Pheophorbide a could induce significant anti-proliferative effects in several human cancer cell lines [82–84], and is combined as a photosensitizer in photodynamic therapy [85–87]. These studies combined with the results of present study suggest that Pheophorbide a could be a promising candidate for treatment of HPV 16.

Figure 5. Chemical structure comparison of Heme, Chlorophyll a and Pheophorbide a.

Pheophorbide could be produced by digestion of ingested plant matter [84]. It has been found that both worm (*Caenorhabditis elegans*) and mouse mitochondria are able to use this molecule in the form of ad hoc photoheterotrophy [88]. The metabolic production of this substance in human body should be studied in further studies to understand its possible stimulating effect on the immune system.

In addition to cervical cancers, anogenital, head, and neck cancers are also strongly associated with HPV infection [89, 90]. A recent study by Kim et al. [91] identified Pheophorbide a in *Eupatorium perfoliatum* extract as a novel lymphatic vascular activator that is crucial for maintaining tissue fluid homeostasis and immune surveillance. As shown in figure 5, Pheophorbide a has a similar structure to that of human blood hemoglobin and it not only could stop the replication cycle of HPV but also influence the lymphatic system to stop metastasis that could result in other types of cancer. Further studies are required to understand and confirm its mechanisms of action.

As mentioned above, Pheophorbide a is a derivative of chlorophyll a [82, 84]. Chlorophylls are natural pigments commonly found in the human diet, and gaining prominence due to the consumers' increasing preference for natural and health-conscious lifestyle choices. These studies

mentioned in the discussion lead us to a quote by Linus Pauling; “You can trace every sickness, every disease and every ailment to a mineral deficiency”. From this perspective, this statement can be generalised to deficiency of nutritional elements, vitamins and their derivatives, which is complimentary with the “food as medicine” philosophy of Hippocrates [92]. The results of this study and previous studies [53-57, 93-95] also suggest the feasibility of this approach. Further studies combined with genomics and pharmaceutical techniques on various diseases could widen our understanding of nutritional medicine that states the interconnectedness of human health and the nutrition.

5. Conclusion

This study identified a stable region in the HPV genome, specifically the HPV E7 CR3 domain, which plays a critical regulatory role in the virus. The molecular docking analysis highlighted Pheophorbide a ($C_{35}H_{36}N_4O_5$) as a potential antiviral molecule that could interact with this target protein, suggesting its possible use in HPV treatment. Given that Pheophorbide a is already used in cancer therapies, its application in HPV treatment represents a promising avenue for future research. Further clinical and *in vitro* validation of these findings could yield valuable insights into human cell-HPV interactions and provide us new tool for HPV treatments.

Article Information Form

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Data Availability Statement

The sequence data of this study are openly available in the NCBI database. Supplementary materials are accessible with this article hosted by the publisher, and also available online: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28028489>

The Declaration of Conflict of Interest/ Common Interest

No conflict of interest or common interest has been declared by the author.

The Declaration of Ethics Committee Approval

This study does not require ethics committee permission or any special permission.

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